

The Identification of Fault Pattern Fractals for Improved Oil and Gas Recovery: A New Process to Identify and Describe Fault Sets Using Non-Linear Methods

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SUMMARY

Unexpected faults are a serious production problem in numerous, complex and compartmentalised oil and gas fields, and are often the single most important restraint on recovery. Fractal mathematics has demonstrated a surprising degree of order in many natural, apparently random systems. It has been shown that fault patterns exhibit a similar order which could be used to indicate the presence of structures missed in the original interpretation of the seismic data and to predict faults below the approximate 20 m limit of seismic resolution. The potential for greater clarity and resolution opened up by this method may greatly aid field description and reservoir production.

We will discuss the development of a comprehensive fault pattern characterisation quantitatively with a set of parameters arising from non-linear methods of analysis. This allows for the standardised comparison of seismic interpretations and a precise method for testing interpretations from the same dataset.

We will show how fractal mathematics may give a measure of the density of the fault set, the number of faults below the limit of seismic resolution, resolve small fault clusters below the limit of seismic resolution and aid in the description and analysis of fault sets.

INTRODUCTION: PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Fault systems are complex three-dimensional deformation structures in the Earth's crust. They commonly form traps for oil and gas, resulting in oil companies spending a great deal of time and money acquiring, processing and interpreting seismic data to image structures. The interpretations represent the intersection between the fault system and a structured geological surface in the form of a seismic horizon (Figure 1). 2D seismic interpretations are the primary exploration tool of oil companies, and the more dense 3D seismic data grids are often used at the field prediction stage. Here the detailed structural maps result-

ing from the 3D seismic interpretations are used to plan drilling programmes and field development.

Fig. 1. The Haltern Terrace offshore mid-Norway. Interpretation of fault pattern from a regional 2D seismic dataset.

Despite the importance of faults in many reservoirs that act as barriers to fluid flow, hardly anything is known about the numerous faults smaller than the resolution limit of seismic data, which is usually about 20 m (i.e. faults with vertical displacements smaller than 20 m go unnoticed, or a fault with a middle segment having less throw will appear as two different and unconnected faults). The primary objective of the project is to find a way of predicting the pattern of small faults below seismic resolution in reservoirs.

Also to be addressed in the project is the natural complexity of fault systems. Complex faulting leads to increasing ambiguity of interpretation, for example, faults could be incorrectly connected, leading to erroneous predictions of reservoir properties. In order to assess the reasonability of seismic interpretation beyond the geological intuition and qualitative reasoning of interpreters, it is necessary to be able to describe quantitatively the interpretations. Due to the complex and inherently non-linear nature of most fault patterns, only a method based on non-linear mathematical concepts will be sufficiently powerful to handle any fault pattern. One of the most fundamental of these concepts is fractal geometry; another is the related concept of percolation theory. Once a general method is easily available, it is possible to exert detailed, quantitative quality control on seismic interpretations by checking the numerical effects of alternative interpretations of the same set. Also, it would offer a standardised comparison of seismic interpretations from different areas, and allow users to develop a reference database. It would also meet the needs for an industry standard for fault pattern characterisation to be used in discussions between companies.

In this paper we will be focusing on the method we have developed for fault characterisation and a generalised description of the resulting computer program, rather than the sub-seismic fault prediction method, on which work is in progress.

FRACTAL THEORY: TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

The development of man's understanding of physical entities has classically concentrated on Euclidian-geometry methods. This has worked well for phenomena that involve only a small range of scales but usually fails to describe entities for which a large range of scales is essential. The orthodox shapes of geometry (triangles, circles, spheres, etc.) lose their structure when magnified, so that a circle viewed on a large enough scale appears as a featureless straight line. Many entities, such as mountains, clouds and coastlines, have irregular or fragmented features which can be modelled to display the same detailed structure over a large range of scales; this is known as 'self-similarity'. Not only do entities with self-similarity display structure at all scales, they also display approximately the same structure on all scales. Mandelbrot (1967) invented the

term 'fractal' to describe a geometrical object that continues to exhibit detailed structure over a large range of scales. Mandelbrot's informal definition is:

A fractal is a shape made of parts that are similar to, or repeat the whole in some way. (Quoted in Feder 1988)

Featureless curves are one-dimensional objects whose length can be precisely defined between two points. However, a fractal curve contains an infinite variety of detail at each point along the curve so that the total length can not be defined. The outline of a mountain shows more detail the closer the observation, so that the shape of the mountain is mimicked in the ledges and boulders and eventually in the shapes of fragmented grains of sand. The overall length of the fractal curve tends towards infinity at larger and larger scales.

A fractal set can be defined thus:

$$N_n = C/r_n^D \quad (1)$$

where N_n is the number of objects (fragments) with a similar linear dimension r_n , C is a constant of proportionality and D is the fractal dimension. If the fractal dimension is an integer then it is equivalent to a Euclidian dimension, i.e. zero for a point, one for a line, two for a square and three for a cube. Generally, the fractal dimension, D , is not an integer but a fraction of Euclidian dimensions, such that a fractal curve described in two dimensional space will have a value between one and two, and similarly in three dimensional space will have a value between two and three. The fractal dimension is essentially a measure of roughness for a line or surface, or openness for a structure like a fault pattern.

The fractal dimension D can be derived from (1) thus:

$$D = \ln(N_{n+1}/N_n)/\ln(r_n/r_{n+1}) \quad (2)$$

when \ln is a logarithm to the base e .

An example of a continuous fractal construction is the triadic Koch island, otherwise known as the snowflake curve (Figure 2, Mandelbrot 1983). The Koch island begins with an equilateral triangle (Figure 2a) with three sides of unit length, $N_0 = 3$, $r_0 = 1$, onto which are placed equilateral triangles with sides of length $r_1 = 1/3$ (Figure 2b). This is the first iteration of the process and order one in the power-law distribution. At this order there are 12 sides so $N_1 = 12$ (Figure 2b). Order two is constructed by placing equilateral triangles of length $r_2 = 1/9$ in the centre of each side such that $N_2 = 48$ (Figure 2c). From (2), $D = \ln 4/\ln 3 = 1.26186$ for the outline of the island. The fractal dimension, D , is between the Euclidian dimensions one and two, a line and surface respectively. The process

can be continued to infinite order with the sides being scale invariant resulting in a picture of a side at any scale being identical. The perimeter, length, of the Koch island increases as n increases, such that as n approaches infinity so does the perimeter length.

Fig. 2. Triadic Koch Island

The Koch island can be considered as a schematic model for a coastline, a mountain, a continental shelf, a contour on a map or possibly a geological bedding plane (cross-section). However, there are two important differences between the model and the real world analogues. First, the perimeter of the Koch island is deterministic and therefore identically scale invariant at all scales. The perimeter of a coast is statistically variable at different scales. A coastline is said to be a statistical fractal. The second difference is the range of scales over which fractal behaviour extends. The Koch island construction has a maximum scale of the original triangle but extends over an infinite range of smaller scales. However, a coastline has both a maximum and minimum scale, the minimum being the scale of the grain size of the rocks. Upper and lower bounds are typical of naturally occurring fractal systems.

Fig. 3. The length of the coast of Britain (P) as a function of length (r). Fractal dimension (D) equals 1.25.

Mandelbrot used the coast of Britain to demonstrate fractal dimensions and self-similarity (Mandelbrot 1967). To quantify these features of fractals he determined the length of the perimeter of Britain which is given by

$$P_n = r_n N_n \quad (3)$$

where r_n is the side length at order n and N_n is the number of sides. Using a map of the coastline, the length was obtained by using dividers of different lengths, r_n . The length of the coastline was plotted against the divider length on log-log paper for the appropriate scale (Figure 3). This demonstrated that the coastline is a fractal, has a fractal dimension of 1.25 and additionally is statistically scale invariant.

Fractal geometries have subsequently been demonstrated in many natural systems, with the number of examples steadily increasing. Topography of all forms is often fractal and was the first to be demonstrated. Contour lines on maps of topography and isopachs have been shown to be fractal. The Earth's surface topography is primarily the result of erosional processes and generally gives a fractal dimension of 1.20 ± 0.05 no matter what the underlying tectonic regime or age. However, young terrains are not necessarily fractal; new volcanic edifices are not fractal nor are the form of alluvial fans. In the case of the form of alluvial fans the governing process is time dependent, that is linear, and therefore not scale invariant; however, the drainage system that generates the fans is a fractal network and the areal distribution of a large number of alluvial fans is probably fractal. The dominant features in the oceans, mid-ocean ridges and trenches are not fractal, having characteristic lengths resulting from linear processes.

FRactal Scaling and Dimension

In Mandelbrot's classic paper (1967) he argued that coastlines are scaling, in the sense that they do not have a specific, or intrinsic length scale, or some narrow scale range. One may introduce an arbitrary and artificial length scale by measuring the length of the coast with a yardstick, and record the length in terms of that unit. But the length is not going to be independent of the chosen length of the yardstick; the coastline does not have a specific and characteristic total length. Instead the length one obtains is going to be a function of the choice of yardstick length, and Mandelbrot showed that the functional relationship is that of a power function. He also found that a power-law relationship was a mathematical equivalent to the geometrical property of self-similarity. In this case the wiggly line of the coast appears to be similar, or has the same degree of wiggleness to it, independent of the scale at which one observes it (Figure 4). In order for this to be the case, the line has to be hierarchical, meaning that the

Fig. 4. The concept of self-similarity (from GeoWissen No. 2 1990).

larger wiggles are composed of smaller ones. This nested hierarchical structure is the essence of fractality.

A fractal dimension is a measure of the density of this hierarchy. Consider the three cases shown in Figure 5. They all start from the same generator, shown to the left, but develop accordingly to slightly different mathematical rules to the structures at the right after three iterations of the generator. Figure 5b is based on the simplest rule, a straightforward repetition of the generator at each iteration, while Figures 5A and 5C have some additional rules, such as having all lines parallel to the first two, or alternating the direction of the leg for each iteration. These structures are only incipient fractals (prefractals) because they do not span a large scale range (only three iterations have been performed). They already have the fundamental hierarchical character of fractals, but their complete fractal nature will only appear after a large number of iterations.

Fig. 5. The relationship between hierarchical scaling and orientation.

The fractal dimension D , measures the openness of the structure when going from one scale to another. Figure 6 (plot of r vs. N for the cases $D = 1, 2$, and 1.585) illustrates the meaning of the dimension. For $D = 1$, decreasing the scale

means that there is just the same number of elements irrespective of scale. This property is only possible if the structure is a straight line but not for a nested hierarchy. For $D = 1.585$, there are many more smaller elements than larger, and so more elements appear as you scale down resulting in a constant density. For $D = 2$, the elements at all scales are indistinguishable, which is only possible if the structure fills a plane perfectly. Therefore, the fractal dimension can be seen as a measure of the plane-filling ability of the structure if the value is between one and two (or the volume-filling ability of the structure if the value is between two and three).

Fig. 6. Fractal dimension as a measure of openness of a scaling hierarchy.

FRACTAL GEOMETRY OF FAULT SETS

The coastline discussed above is simply a wiggly line, whereas a fault set is actually formed of discrete elements. It is possible to treat the fault set as a whole using the standard technique of box-counting, which is a method for finding the fractal dimension. The resulting parameters apply strictly to the set as a whole, with the method not distinguishing between the length contributed by the complex wiggleness of a large fault, and the length contributed by including more and more small faults, nor does it take into account whether a given part of the fault set is a segment of a larger, a single, or a branching fault.

Individual faults sets can be defined as discrete, quasi-linear, and unbranch-

ing elements. With this definition one can find the number of faults at any given length scale. This approach ignores wiggleness, and treats the faults as linear elements, which, when cumulated, or recorded as a cumulative distribution, give an insight to the fractal geometry of the fault set. Both approaches will ideally yield power-law distributions over a large scale range. The non-cumulative distributions should have the same fractal parameters if the elements are in fact linear. If the faults are not exactly linear, the difference in fractal dimension obtained by the two methods is a measure of the contribution of wiggleness to the box-counting fractal dimension.

The fractal geometry can be further described by considering the interaction of individual units. Due to this interaction, units commonly join together to form branching structures or clusters, which are subsets of the whole set. Such clusters may well be self-similar in their own right. The elementary cluster consists of two faults, and larger clusters are built by successively adding elementary clusters onto each other. The final outcome is a large branching structure.

Generally, the size distribution of fault clusters is scaling with specific characteristics, thereby contributing significantly to the observed fractal geometry. Such fault interactions are completely ignored by the methods described above, requiring a cluster size-number distribution in addition. Cluster size is recorded as total length within a cluster measured at a given length scale. This enables the possibility of measuring fault length distribution parameters within clusters, such as the fractal dimension, as a function of cluster size. However, in many cases there will be insufficient fault data for this method.

In the following sections the description of the fractal geometry of a fault set will be discussed in four ways: 1) as a whole via box counting, 2) as a set of elements via fault length distribution, 3) as a set of clusters via percolation, 4) as a set of orientations via circular statistics.

BOX COUNTING: SEEING THE FAULT SET AS A WHOLE

Box-counting is a numerical method for find the scaling properties of the fault set, or any pattern, as a whole. Box counting is essentially a numerical microscope. As the boxes become smaller, they record more detail of the pattern, with each step in the scaling down process equivalent to increasing the resolution by a factor of 2. The method can be applied to any pattern, but only fractals yield a straight line interval over a scale range of more than one order of magnitude. The process of box-counting is illustrated in Figure 7. It consists of overlaying the pattern with a square grid, and counting the number of gridcells, or boxes, that contain a part of the pattern. The largest box size possible is given by having one box spanning the whole pattern. This box has a side length, $r(1)$. The box is then subdivided into four equal boxes with side length $r(2) = r(1)/2$. At this stage perhaps only two or three boxes contain a part of the pattern.

Turcotte 1992

N = 98
r = 1Km

N = 270
r = 0.5 Km

Fig. 7. The box-counting procedure (from Turcotte 1991).

The process is repeated for increasingly smaller boxes. The number of boxes, N , with a given side length, r , that is needed to cover the set is plotted against r in a log-log plot. If the pattern is scaling the function $N(r)$ is a power-law described by $N(r) = ar^{-D_B}$ where D_B is the box-counting fractal dimension, and a = amplitude is the constant term of an applied regression line (the intersection of the regression line with the y-axis).

Figure 8 is the outcome of box-counting the Halten Terrace (Figure 1). It shows a fractal extending to ca. 2 orders of magnitude below the limit of seismic resolution, giving a fractal dimension of 1.63 for the pattern. The straight line indicates more detail is visible with each resolving step down according to a power-law.

In nature, fractals only exist over a finite scale range, and so two more parameters need to be estimated; the lower and upper natural cutoff. The upper cutoff is the side length of the box or circle which encapsulates the pattern. The lower cutoff is much more difficult to estimate, since for a fault system it presumably extends several orders of magnitude below the seismic resolution threshold and the distance between seismic lines in a 3D grid. The lower cutoff can only be inferred from analogue outcrop data, and qualitatively from cores. Core data from the Halten Terrace indicate that faults extend at least down to the millimetre scale.

Fig. 8. Box-counting of the Halten Terrace dataset.

Fractals tend to be very open structured and with low density. The total length of the faults in the fractal will go towards infinity, as the area enclosing the fractal goes asymptotically towards a finite size. The length increase stems from adding detail, not from expanding the structure. In general, fractals existing over many orders of magnitude seem massive when viewed from a distance, but have a very low mass when viewed close up. For example, if all the faults of the Halten Terrace could be digitised with their true widths, and put next to each other in a completely plane-filling arrangement, they would span only a small fraction of their present area. Fractals do not have an intrinsic, or characteristic length, and this translates into a lack of a specific density.

Both the amplitude and the fractal dimension can be turned into independent measures of density of the fractal structure. The fractal dimension can be viewed as a density measure since it records the ability of the pattern to fill the plane. But the fractal dimension is only partly related to density.

The amplitude is more closely related to density than the fractal dimension and is also independent of the fractal dimension. The amplitude is a measure of the number of elements present at each scale. If the amplitude is low, even a fractal dimension very close to two would not generate a plane-filling structure in an intuitive sense.

The amplitude can be converted to a density measure by dividing it by the total length of the fault set measured at the lower natural cutoff (set at 100 m, Stølum 1991). The amplitude is then converted into a dimensionless number, the normalised amplitude, a_n , which is a measure of the density of the whole fractal, $a_n = N_B(r=1 \text{ km})/N_B(r=0.10 \text{ km})$. The normalised amplitude records a density measure of the whole fractal, since at $a_n = 0$, $D_B = 0$, the fault system has density equal to zero, while at $a_n = 1$, $D_B = 2$, the system is completely plane-filling if the fractal scales down over an infinite range. For intermediate values the fractal areal coverage is measured by the two parameters, but more sensitively by a_n than D_B . We are currently developing a single measure of fractal density combining both parameters.

FAULT LENGTH DISTRIBUTION: SEEING THE FAULT PATTERN AS A SET OF ELEMENTS

Each fault in a seismic interpretation does not appear to be fractal. There is a certain wiggleness to larger faults; not enough to constitute self-similarity but each fault can be described as a quasi-linear feature. Some faults will be linear features, others will have minor wiggles and some will be bent or evenly curved. At the outset we have treated this variability as secondary, and considered all faults as linear, with the straight line between the endpoints being a reasonable estimate of fault length. (This first-order representation will be improved in a later version of the computer program.)

Fig. 9A. Fault length distribution of the Halten Terrace dataset.

Fig. 9B. Close-up of the distribution in Figure 9A.

In this way, each fault is represented by a finite length, and the fault length distribution is an attribute of the whole set when seen as a set of single faults. Figure 9A is a plot of length frequency vs. sample bin size with a resulting distribution close to lognormal. This, however, does not reflect any underlying process, but is an artifact of sampling. Very small faults are under-represented since they are close to the seismic resolution threshold. Also the point representing the largest bin size is likely to be subject to sampling error.

For one or two very long faults in the system, their length and number will be strongly affected by a single interpretational error such as connecting, or failing to connect, two long fault segments. If we disregard these points, we are left with four points, shown in Figure 9B which follow an exponential distribution. The semilog plot in Figure 10 shows how this distribution may be used to estimate the number of faults below the limit of seismic resolution.

Fig. 10. Extrapolation function based on Figure 9B.

It may be argued that the lengths are not the true lengths, but the visible lengths above the seismic resolution limit. This introduces a biasing error, giving rise to a disproportionately high number of small faults since the shorter the fault, and the smaller the displacement, the more it will be affected by this error. As a result, the distribution may not be exponential, but a power-law. We are currently studying this possibility empirically, by looking at large, onshore, active fault systems, where sampling error is considerably smaller. If that turns out to be an important factor, an analytical correction should be applied in order to transform the exponential distribution to the appropriate power-law distribution.

Fig. 11. Method of clustering of faults.

PERCOLATION: SEEING THE FAULT PATTERN
AS A SET OF CLUSTERS

Faults are unevenly distributed and invariably form clusters which, in the simplest case, takes the form of direct fault interaction; one fault terminates in another, giving rise to a branching structure. Faults are also generally far apart, giving rise to gaps or areas devoid of faults, as well as a differential degree of connectedness among the faults. Clusters can be identified by the smallest distance, d , between any of the fault ends of any two faults (Figure 11). The clustering procedure consists in setting the distance at a given value, x , and then calculating the distances between all fault pairs, accepting as clusters only those with $d < x$. Once defined, a cluster can also be measured by the total length of the constituent faults, or as a fraction of the length of the total fault set.

CONNECTIVITY INDEX

$$C = 2 \frac{N_f}{N_e} - 1$$

N_f = number of faults

N_e = number of loose fault ends

$$C = 0$$

$$C = 0.20$$

$$C = 0.50$$

$$C = 1$$

Fig. 12. Definition of the connectivity index.

The cluster is described by its constituent faults as well as its characteristic length of distance, *d*. Additionally, a measure is needed to describe how well connected it is. Since clusters consist of faults that are closer together than the average for the set as a whole, they should also have a higher degree of actual fault connections than the whole set. We suggest to measure connectivity by a simple parameter, *C*, defined and explained in Figure 12. Also, a cluster may well have a significantly different box-counting fractal dimension, and amplitude from the whole set, since it is likely to have a higher fault density. Individual clusters may also have a distinct fault length distribution and orientation and orientation pattern.

Fig. 13A. Cluster frequency distribution.

Fig. 13B. Close-up of part of the distribution in Figure 13A.

In looking at different fault sets, we notice a characteristic variation in cluster geometry. For small datasets, clusters may well be separated, discrete, aggregates with a high internal connectivity and similar density, and there may even be a characteristic cluster size. Large datasets with hundreds of faults, like the Halten Terrace fault system, tend to exhibit a cluster geometry with a few highly distinct clusters, and fault distances seem to form a diffuse continuum rather than discrete steps. Yet there are gaps and density differences, and so the dataset is clustered, but in a way which is less intuitively obvious than in the first instance. In order to handle this far more complex situation we are using a method based on percolation theory.

According to percolation theory, there is a critical threshold, at which the largest cluster of many small clusters, changes to include enough faults to reach from one side of the areal perimeter of the fault set to the opposite, thereby changing the properties of the system as a whole from non-connected to connected (from 'non-percolating' to 'percolating').

Figure 13A shows a cluster frequency distribution against distance, d . The greatest distance is that necessary to form a single cluster which spans the whole dataset. The distribution appears lognormal, but again this is due to sampling bias as the smallest distance approaches the distance between the seismic lines. There are only a few small clusters having d smaller than this distance, which is related to the areal resolution threshold of the seismic data. Ignoring this part of the curve, we find a very good fit to an exponential distribution (Figure 13B). The semilog plot in Figure 14 shows how this distribution can be used to estimate the number of clusters below the limit of seismic resolution which exist in the actual fault set.

Fig. 14. Extrapolation based on Figure 13D.

Fig. 15. Growth of largest cluster as a function of increasing distance.

In deriving this distribution, it appears that as d increases, a large cluster is formed by coalescence of tighter clusters which grows to span the whole dataset. Figure 15 is a plot of the growth of the largest cluster as a function of d , and the reduction in connectivity of the largest cluster as the size increase. Both curves are sigmoidal. In clusters formed by a random growth process, the cluster size distribution at the percolation theory critical threshold, $d = d_c$, is fractal. We estimate the critical threshold by the intersection of the connectivity curve with the growth curve. The critical threshold may be an important measure in the examination of fault systems that have controlled the migration of hydrocarbons. Figure 16 shows that the cumulative distribution of clusters with $d = d_c$ follows a power-law, indicating the cluster pattern to be self-similar. The fractal dimension of the clusters, D_c , is 1.70 (Figure 17); distinctly different from the box-counting fractal dimension for the set as a whole. Again these power-law relationships can be used for extrapolation to smaller clusters below the limit of seismic resolution.

Fig. 16. Cumulative distribution of cluster size at the critical distance.

Fig. 17. Estimate of the fractal dimension of clusters at the critical distance.

Fig. 18. Circular distribution of the Halten Terrace fault set.

CIRCULAR STATISTICS: THE FAULT PATTERN AS A SET OF ORIENTATIONS

The basis for our analysis of orientations is the circular distribution, shown in Figure 18 for the Halten Terrace. This distribution is characterised by the vectorial mean and angular deviation, which is equivalent to the mean and standard deviation in linear statistics. The circular distribution can be extracted from any subset formed as clusters or given a certain length interval. The distribution in Figure 18 is bimodal. Multimodality is common in fault sets, and the distribution can be further analysed by isolating segments and obtaining the vectorial mean and angular deviation from different sets of the whole population.

CONCLUSIONS

We have developed the basic framework of a comprehensive fault pattern characterisation computer program, which will enable users to identify and describe fault patterns quantitatively with a set of parameters arising from non-linear methods of analysis. This allows for the standardised comparison of seismic interpretations and a precise method for testing interpretations from the same dataset.

We have shown how the fractal dimension and amplitude can give a measure of the density of the fault set; how the fault length distribution can estimate the number of faults below the limit of seismic resolution; and how the use of circular statistics can aid in the description and analysis of fault sets.

REFERENCES

- Feder, J., 1988, *Fractals*, Plenum Press, New York, 283p.
- Mandelbrot, B.M., 1967, *How long is the coast of Britain? Statistical self-similarity and fractal dimension*, Science 156, 636-8.
- Mandelbrot, B.M., 1983, *The Fractal Geometry of Nature*, 2nd ed., Freeman, San Francisco, 351p.
- Stølum, H-H., 1991, *Fractal heterogeneity of clastic reservoirs*, in Lake, L.W., Carol, H.B. and Wesson, T. Reservoir Characterisation II, Academic Press, San Diego, 579-612.
- Turcotte, D.L., 1992, *Fractals and Chaos in Geology and Geophysics*, Cambridge University Press, 221p.

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